

King's Type 1 Diabetes Service Resource Pack

September 2020

This document serves as a support pack with resources and links to support your diabetes management in between clinic appointments

Please also follow us on twitter @diabeteskings where we will post up to date resources and research findings, our website also has links which you may find useful

<https://www.kch.nhs.uk/service/a-z/diabetes>

General Type 1 Diabetes websites

➤ **T1 Resources** - www.t1resources.uk

Search engine where you can find information to help manage all aspects of living with Type 1 diabetes.

➤ **My Type 1 Diabetes** - <https://mytype1diabetes.nhs.uk/>

A public information website that is accessible to all. The 'Know More' section has searchable resources including videos and leaflets, and multi-language content in the My Languages section (no registration required).

Four eLearning courses for adults with Type 1 diabetes, to help increase understanding and confidence in self-management. Courses cover a range of topics useful for people who are newly diagnosed, or for those needing additional support with self-management skills, insulin management, carb counting, lifestyle change and complications management. They also include topics like driving, employment, alcohol, sex and travel. There is a specific course for older teenagers and young adults, and courses for people either thinking about or starting insulin pump therapy.

➤ **NHS Type 1 diabetes Website** - <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/type-1-diabetes/>

General advice and links for adults living with type 1 diabetes

➤ **Diabetes UK** - www.diabetes.org.uk

Email – info@diabetes.org.uk

Telephone – 0345 123 2399

Clinical support – 01372 720148 (Mon-Fri 9am-6pm)

News and up to date information on all aspects of living with Type 1 diabetes including Corona virus updates, research and technology, free magazine also available.

➤ **JDRF** – <https://jdrf.org.uk/>

Registered charity funding research to cure, treat and prevent type 1 diabetes. A library of resources to support people with Type 1 diabetes and their families.

➤ **PocketMedic** - <http://pocketmedic.org/links/>

A library of over 50 self-management films to share the experiences of people living with Type 1 diabetes

➤ **Diabetes Research and Wellness Foundation** - <https://www.drwf.org.uk/understanding-diabetes/information-leaflets>

A series of professionally authored leaflets on diabetes and related health which are freely available as pdf download, audio file or as hard copy upon request.

Self-management of Type 1 Diabetes Resources and Carbohydrate counting

- **DAFNE Online** – www.dafneonline.co.uk

Online website for DAFNE graduates, including course handbook, forums, carbohydrate portion lists, and online blood glucose diary. Access code needed from your team.

- **BERTIE** – Type 1 diabetes Education online programme - www.bertieonline.org.uk

Online programme to help the user manage their diabetes in a way that suits their lifestyle

- **ABCD DTN- UK** - <https://abcd.care/dtn/resources?page=1>

Technology in diabetes recourses. Self-management videos and resources supporting patients and healthcare professionals with insulin Pumps, Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM), Libre and CGM in Pregnancy.

- **STEP – Scottish Type 1 Education Programme** - https://www.t1resources.uk/fileadmin/user_upload/downloads/Ten_steps_to_improving_T1_diabetes_control.pdf

10 steps to improving your Type 1 diabetes control

- **Carbs and Cals** - <https://www.carbsandcals.com/>

Book and app that makes carbohydrate counting easier using photos of different portion sizes. You can also subscribe to their YouTube channel for weekly videos on carb counting, diabetes, recipes, takeaways, low-carb & weight loss.

- **Diabetes UK Carbohydrate counting support** - <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/enjoy-food/carbohydrates-and-diabetes/nuts-and-bolts-of-carb-counting>

Basic understanding and resources to start carbohydrate counting and Enjoy food Diabetes UK food book: <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/enjoy-food/eating-with-diabetes>

- **Sheffield Hospital carbohydrate counting videos** - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qDwLSFG38Ms>

YouTube video by the diabetes team in Sheffield around calculating carbohydrates

Bolus Calculators

- **Carbohydrate Calculator chart** - <https://www.ndr-uk.org/uploads/pdf/2201468335335.pdf>
- **Bolus calculator chart** - <https://www.ndr-uk.org/uploads/pdf/2211461925720.pdf>
- **MySugr app** - <https://www.mysugr.com/en/>
- **Mylife Bolus calculator app** - <https://www.mylife-diabetescare.com/en-GB/products/therapy-management/mylife-digital.html>
- **DiabetesM** - <https://www.diabetes-m.com/blog/press-releases/diabetesm-gets-an-ios-version-and-a-premium-subscription-service/>

Speak to your local GP

Ask your GP to refer you to your local diabetic eye screening service. Your GP and/or Practice nurse can also do your annual checks and review.

➤ Eye care:

Diabetes UK – diabetes and eye problems <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/complications/retinopathy>

NHS website – Diabetic eye screening <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/diabetic-eye-screening/>

DECS - For those who live in SE London, contact details are: <https://www.guysandstthomas.nhs.uk/our-services/seldesp/overview.aspx>

➤ Foot care:

Diabetes UK – how to look after your feet: <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/complications/feet/taking-care-of-your-feet>

Trend UK – Looking after your feet when you have Diabetes leaflet: https://mytype1diabetes.nhs.uk/media/3847/a5_foot_trend_final.pdf

East Midlands Diabetes Foot Group advice and information leaflet: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/midlands/wp-content/uploads/sites/46/2019/05/foot-health-moderate-risk.pdf>

Clinic preparation and downloads

Preparation is key and having your data available not only allows you to observe patterns and trends but also makes for a successful consultation.

Are you able to download your blood glucose meter or Insulin pump?

Here are links that may help:

- **Diasend** (can be used for most blood glucose meters and insulin pumps):

www.diasend.com/en/patient

Use the code below to share your downloads with Kings diabetes team.

Clinic ID: 88-20339

- **Medtronic:**

You can download your Medtronic pump using carelink:

<https://carelink.minimed.eu/app/login>

- **Freestyle Libre:**

Register on Libreview and link to King's College Hospital.

To do this go to <http://www.LibreView.com>

Once logged in go to account settings, click my practices and *enter code: 11457101*

- **Dexcom:**

Register on the Clarity account: <http://clarity.dexcom.eu>

Ask your healthcare professional to email you the link to share your data.

Which tests should I be getting?

There are some tests you should be having annually to monitor your ongoing health and to help prevent/slow down long term conditions:

- **Diabetes UK – Know your 15 Healthcare essentials**

<https://www.diabetes.org.uk/Guide-to-diabetes/Managing-your-diabetes/15-healthcare-essentials/What-are-the-15-Healthcare-Essentials>

Managing Illness and Sick day Rules

Managing illness, what to do when you are ill with Type 1 diabetes/sick day rules:

- **Trend UK** -Type 1 Diabetes Sick day rules
https://trend-uk.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/A5_T1Illness_TREND_FINAL.pdf
- **ABCD DTN** – sick day rules when managing an insulin pump
https://abcd.care/sites/abcd.care/files/site_uploads/sick_day_rules_pump_DTN%20logo%201.2.pdf

Hypoglycaemia

Guidance on Treating Hypoglycaemia:

- **Trend UK** – Hypo Guidance https://trend-uk.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/A5_Hypo_TREND.pdf
- **Diabetes UK** – <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/complications/hypos/having-a-hypo>
- **Diabetes.co.uk** - <https://www.diabetes.co.uk/Diabetes-and-Hypoglycaemia.html>

Support and psychological help

- **Diabetes.co.uk** – <https://www.diabetes.co.uk/>

A community of people with diabetes, family members, friends, supporters and carers, offering their own support and first-hand knowledge. The Diabetes Forum is demonstrated in research to be the most actively used social medium for people with diabetes

- **Sugar Buddies** - <http://sugarbuddies.org.uk/>

Peer support group for anyone above the age of 18 with Type 1 diabetes.

Facebook link: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/sugarbuddieshampshire/>

Twitter: @sugarbuddies1

- **iTalk** - Free local talking therapies service – www.italk.org.uk
- **IAPT** - Psychological support - patients can self-refer to local IAPT services - <https://www.nhs.uk/service-search/find-a-psychological-therapies-service/>

Type 1 diabetes and exercise

- **Runsweet** – <http://www.runsweet.com/>

Diabetes and sport, helping people with diabetes become winners.

- **Extod**- <http://www.extod.org/patient-advice>

Website aimed at providing advice and guidance to people with Type 1 diabetes on safely and confidently managing blood glucose levels before, during, and after exercise

- **Excarbs** - <https://excarbs.sansum.org>

Plan Your Insulin, Exercise Safely, Have Fun and Reap the Rewards!

- **JDRF Peak** – <https://www.jdrf.org/t1d-resources/hcp/peak-program/>

JDRF Exercise and Knowledge (PEAK) Program is a unique outreach initiative that gives clear guidance on how to safely pursue exercise. PEAK provides education on the environmental, dietary, and physiologic elements that affect physical activity in those with Type 1 diabetes.

- **DTN-UK** - <https://abcd.care/dtn/education>

Providing education to health care professionals as well as people with diabetes to help them make the best use of diabetes technology and exercise.

Pregnancy

- **DTN-UK** - <https://abcd.care/dtn/CGM>

Online education programme on CGM during pregnancy also including Top Tips during pregnancy:

- Top tips for optimising glucose levels in pregnancy
- Top tips for using your Libre Sensor in pregnancy
- Top tips: Using Dexcom G6 Real-Time CGM in Pregnancy
- Sick day rules in pregnancy for insulin pump users

- **Diabetes UK** – <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/guide-to-diabetes/life-with-diabetes/pregnancy>

Planning for a pregnancy when you have diabetes

Driving and Travel

- **DVLA** - <https://www.gov.uk/driving-medical-conditions>

Information about medical conditions, disabilities and driving

- **Trend** - https://trend-uk.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/A5_6pp_Driving_TREND_CONNECT.pdf

Safe driving and diabetes leaflet

- **Diabetestravel.org** - <https://diabetestravel.sansum.org/results/>

Here is advice on what you should do before going on holiday. Speak to your diabetes team if needed at least 2 weeks before you go away. Also check you have appropriate insurance.

COVID-19 and Type 1 Diabetes

A Compendium of helpful Resources for People Living with Diabetes during COVID-19 Pandemic by County Durham and Darlington Diabetes Team -

https://docs.google.com/document/d/17MI9J5nL8lrkuOGsv4pe_u_KvdmxRrpLT4aXdtDoeOE/edit

- **Diabetes UK** - www.diabetes.org.uk/about_us/news/coronavirus

- **Association of British Clinical Diabetologists (ABCD)** - www.abcd.care/covid19/advice-patients

- **Team 101** - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3835968#.XsVltF47hV1.mailto>

101Diabetes team FAQ's about Diabetes and COVID-19 following the latest data published (19/5/2020).

- **Mental Health Europe** - <https://www.mhe-sme.org/covid-19/>

8 ways to look after your mental health during Covid-19

- **FACE COVID** – <https://youtu.be/BmvNCdpHUYM>

YouTube video, 'How to respond effectively to the corona crisis' by Dr Russ Harris